

Comparison of CHM15k extinction and mass products from ALICE net, A-Profiles and the UK Met Office.

Martin Osborne, Francesca Barnaba, Annachiara Bellini, Joelle Buxmann, Henri Diemoz, Maxime Hervo, Ina Mattis, Augustine Mortier, Frank Wagner.

Abstract.

Height resolved aerosol extinction coefficient and mass concentration profiles are routinely estimated from Automatic Low-power Lidar and Ceilometer (ACL) data by several met services and research institutions around Europe. In this study we compare these products retrieved using a standard workflow from three networks / institutions, ALICE net in Italy (Dionisi et al. 2018; Bellini et al., 2024), Met Norway (A-Profiles – methods described in Mortier et al. 2013) and the UK Met Office (e.g. Osborne et al. 2019). The purpose of this study is to investigate the sources of differences, not to assess the methods within each workflow. The estimates are using the standard [E-PROFILE - Eumetnet](#) L2 CHM15k data product, and where available sun-sky photometer data is also used in the UK Met Office calculations. Four data sets were chosen that either represented interesting events and / or also presented the opportunity for co-located in-situ “truth” measurements or high powered lidar data that could be used to assess the ALC estimates. The comparison showed that all workflows produce comparable and physically reasonable results. The extinction coefficient products from the three workflows were very similar (often with 15% of each other), and the differences were mainly due to the choice of lidar ratio (LR). The mass estimates were sometimes significantly different (200% in some cases). As expected, these differences are almost entirely due to the choice of extinction coefficient to mass conversion (EMC) factors. A detailed study on the methods of obtaining EMCs, and a related climatology of EMCs for various aerosol types and aerosol mixtures compiled for 1064nm and 910nm would be beneficial for the Automatic Ceilometer and Lidars (ALC) community.

1. Introduction.

Several institutions involved in PROBE operate networks of ALC for the monitoring of the atmospheric boundary layer and free troposphere. As well as cloud base height and attenuated backscatter, the estimation of height resolved aerosol extinction coefficient and mass concentration profiles from lidar and ACL data is a long-established practice (e.g. Ansmann et al. 2012, Hervo et al. 2012, Mortier et al. 2013, Dionisi et al. 2018, Osborne et al. 2019, 2021). With the central processing and data availability offered by EUMETNET’s E-Profile program, unified European scale products for both aerosol extinction coefficient and mass concentration could be obtainable from ALC data. However, there are several challenges to address before this can be done. As discussed in other studies within PROBE, the calibration of the ALC data is especially important where a forward Klett method (Klett 1985) is employed to calculate aerosol backscatter or extinction coefficients, and the seasonal variation of this is still to be fully addressed. In the overlap region on ALC’s with non-coaxial transmitters and receivers, the data should be corrected as far as possible for both overlap effects and associated temperature variation (Hervo et al. 2016). This study does not seek to make any assessment of either of these corrections, which could be performed using different methods in the three networks. Rather the calibration applied in the E-Profile L2 data product is used in all three workflows. Similarly, the manufacturers overlap correction is assumed to be correct (although as outlined in the next section in some cases this is then corrected for temperature effects using the technique in Hervo et al. 2016). This is intended to be representative of the results that would be obtained should a workflow be implemented within E-Profile E. The study is intended to assess if the three workflows result in similar estimates for extinction coefficient and mass concentration, and to identify sources of differences.

This report is organised as follows. Section 2 provides some background on the general principles used by the three workflows. Section 3 gives a description of the four sets of ALC data and associated ancillary data. Section 4 presents the results and some discussion, and section 5 provides conclusions and recommendations.

2. Background.

The A-Profiles and UK Met Office workflows used in this study use the same general principle of first obtaining an extinction coefficient profile from the ALC attenuated backscatter data, and then dividing this by EMCs to convert the extinction coefficient to a mass concentration. ALICEnet is different and first links backscatter to particle volume, and then using an assumed density to convert this to mass (more detail is given below). To aid the comparison of the three workflows, the resulting effective MCF that would convert the ALICEnet extinction coefficient to the estimated mass concentration is reported in this study.

The EMC is often referred to as “specific extinction” in the wider literature, but we use EMC here to be consistent within the PROBE community. The EMC is in units of m^2g^{-1} and can be thought of as a value representing the “extinction per unit mass concentration” for a particular type of aerosol particle. The EMC is wavelength specific and is dependent on particle composition (refractive index), density, shape, size, and hydration. This makes the choice of EMC difficult, as what is appropriate for one aerosol plume may not be appropriate for another, even if they are comprised of the same aerosol type.

As outlined in the previous section, the L2 E-Profile CHM15k data product is used in this study, and no further calibration is applied. The E-Profile calibration procedure identifies clear, non-cloudy, night-time profiles and uses a backward (or inward) Klett in which a “calibration region” in the free troposphere is assumed to be aerosol free, and within which the CHM15k is receiving a molecular backscatter signal only. The theoretical value of this molecular only signal is calculated from a temperature and pressure profile (either from a standard atmosphere, model data or radiosonde measurement) and the multiplication factor that brings the measured signal together with the theoretical signal is the calibration constant. This calibration constant is then applied to all profiles to obtain attenuated backscatter measurements. The ALC extinction coefficient and mass concentration estimated presented in this study are the result of forward (or outward) Klett methods only, and no further attempt is made to calibrate the data using reference range molecular signals.

The following sub-sections briefly describe the methods used in each of the three workflows.

ALICEnet.

The L2 data are cloud screened from the cloud base heights detected by the ALCs down to -0.5 km below it. In the operational Alicenet workflow, a specific Alicenet procedure (different from the E-Profile one) is used for both molecular calibration and overlap correction (Bellini et al., 2024). The retrieval of aerosol backscatter and extinction coefficient profiles is based on the forward Klett inversion with variable lidar ratios. These latter are in fact not fixed a-priori but rather obtained using a polynomial function linking aerosol backscatter to aerosol extinction coefficients (a mean ‘continental type’ aerosol is used for this purpose as described in Dionisi et al. (2018)), and an iterative technique until convergence of the backscatter profile. The parameters assumed in the inversion are thus the polynomial coefficients, the first guess LR value (operatively a value $\text{LR} = 38\text{sr}$ is used, compatible with CALIPSO at 1064 nm for continental polluted/clean aerosols, Omar et al., 2009), and the molecular profile (standard atmosphere). The retrieval is based solely on ALC data (no ancillary information e.g. sun-sky photometer data is used).

The retrieval of the aerosol mass profiles is based on a polynomial function linking the retrieved aerosol backscatter directly to the aerosol volume (Dionisi et al., 2018). This is done again assuming a ‘continental aerosol type’. Therefore, there is no specific assumption of EMC factors, and the backscatter-to-volume conversion is variable with height, being driven by the functional relationship

mentioned above. Once the aerosol volume profile is obtained, the relevant aerosol mass concentration one is derived assuming an aerosol density which is typically chosen according to the dominant aerosol type, as based on ancillary information when available. In this a value of 1.5 gcm⁻³ (here kept uniform in time and range) was assumed as mean value for continental-type aerosol. This is in contrast to the A-Profiles and the UK Met Office workflows, which, as described below, use different densities for different aerosol types. This difference is highlighted in the Hohenpeißenberg example in section 4.

A-Profiles.

A-Profiles is an extensive Python library for reading and processing ALC measurements. The library supports E-Profile ceilometer data formats. The library includes several modules such as clouds detection, tracking of the planetary boundary layer height or the retrieval of aerosol extinction coefficient, and mass concentration. The library offers far more functionality than is assessed here and can be configured to run with many different options for cloud screening, time and height averaging, and choices of a-priori factors. We use it here in a basic mode using the native time and height resolution of the E-Profile L2 data. Unlike the other two workflows the CHM15k data is not corrected for temperature effects in the overlap region. The aerosol extinction module is used here with a fixed LR of 40sr and a backward Klett method. The library is also capable of using an inward Klett method (not assessed here as this requires user intervention). The EMCs are calculated using Mie scattering calculations (at 1064nm) and size distributions, refractive indices, and densities for various aerosols from the literature (e.g. volcanic ash as shown in fig. 1A).

Figure1. Methods used in the calculation of EMCs by (A) A-Profiles and (B) the UK Met Office.

UK-Met Office.

The E-Profile L2 data are cloud screened using only the ALC detected cloud levels as already reported in the L2 file, and the data is processed at the L2 native time and range resolution. The overlap temperature correction, as calculated by MeteoSwiss, is applied. Extinction coefficient profiles are obtained using a forward Klett method with a fixed LR of 50sr. Where sun-sky photometer size distributions are available, EMCs are calculated from AOD and size distribution measurements. This method largely follows the methodology used in the POLYPHON technique (e.g. Ansmann et. al 2019) in which the fine and coarse mode AODs reported by the AERONET spectral deconvolution algorithm (SDA) are combined with the fine and coarse mode volumes and assumed densities for each mode (see also Ansmann et al. 2012). The SDA provides values at 500nm only, and so they are not suitable for calculating values to convert extinctions at 1064nm. Therefore T-Matrix scattering calculations are performed on the fine mode (sub 1 micron radius) size distribution to calculate an AOD at 1064nm (no scattering calculations are made for particles larger than 1 micron in radius). This fine mode AOD value

is then subtracted from the total AOD at 1064 as measured by the sun-photometer. In this way, separate estimates for the AOD for fine and coarse mode at 1064nm are obtained. These are then divided by the respective volumes for the fine and coarse modes, giving factors for “extinction per unit volume”. This is then combined with literature values for density to arrive at EMCs for fine and coarse mode aerosols (fig. 1B). These can then either be applied separately or combined in the same ratio as the fine and coarse mode volumes. Where no sun-photometer data are available, default values from previous AERONET measurements are used.

Table 1. Summary of workflows used in this study.

Workflow	Backscatter method	EMC	Ancillary data used?
ALICENet	Forward Klett in which the LR is not fixed a-priori but based on aerosol backscatter-to-extinction ratios driven by pre-computed polynomial functional relationships based on a continental-type aerosol model. Such variable LR is thus also variable with height.	ALICENET does not assume EMC values but makes use of a polynomial function linking aerosol backscatter to aerosol volume. Aerosol mass is then obtained assuming a density value which is chosen according to the dominating aerosol type.	No
AProfiles	Forward Klett LR =40sr	From Mie scattering calculation on idealised size distributions and assumed densities for different aerosol types.	No
UK Met Office	Forward Klett LR=50sr	Derived from T-Matrix scattering calculations and Aeronet size distributions and assumed densities for different aerosol types.	Yes – where available AERONET data is used to constrain the EMC.

3. Data.

After discussions between the authors, four CHM15k data sets were identified that represented three aerosol types: urban / anthropogenic pollution, biomass burning aerosol and desert dust. Fig. 3 shows plots of the calibrated L2 attenuated backscatter data (with y-axis showing range from the instrument and not altitude), and table 2 summarises the aerosol types and ancillary data available. The aerosol types were confirmed by model back trajectories (not shown here).

Table 2. Summary of data used in this study.

Location	Date	Aerosol type	Ancillary data/Truth value	Truth value	Institution
Aosta Lon:7.35 Lon: 45.74 Elevation: 560 masl	26 May 2017	Anthropogenic pollution	Sky-net sun-photometer	None	ARPA (ARPA VDA – Agenzia Regionale per la Protezione dell’Ambiente Valle d’Aosta), Valle d’Aosta

Rome Lon: 12.65 Lat: 41.84 Elevation: 130 masl	11 July 2017	Anthropogenic pollution mixed with local biomass burning and some residual desert dust	Co-located Aeronet sun- photometer	In-situ airborne measurements from a GRIMM particle counter	(National Research Council- Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate, CNR- ISAC).
Kleine Scheidegg Lon: 46.59 Lat: 7.96 Elevation: 2061 masl	30 September 2023	Biomass Burning	None	Particle counter at 1300 m above CHM15k (3 km horizontal separation)	MeteoSwiss
Hohenpeißenberg Lon: 11.01 Lat: 47.80 Elevation: 990 masl	21 June 2020	Desert Dust	Aeronet sun- photometer	PollyXT lidar data at 532 nm	Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD)

Figure 2. CHM15k EPROFILE L2 24h data used in this study. (A) Aosta for 26 May 2017 and (B) Rome TV for 11 July 2017. Both sites part of ALICE net. (C) Hohenpeißenberg for 21 June 2023. Instrument operated by DWD and (D) Kleine Scheidegg for 30 September 2023. Instrument operated by MeteoSwiss

Aosta.

This example is a relatively cloud free day, and the aerosol load within the boundary layer is likely anthropogenic pollution. At the time this data was recorded, Aosta had a Skynet Prede-POM sun-sky photometer (Takamura and Nakajima 2004) providing AOD measurements and size distributions – shown in figure 3a. Clear peaks in the sub-micron, fine mode are consistent with anthropogenic pollution.

Figure 3. Size distributions from sun-photometers co-located with CHM15k ALCs. (A) SKYnet sun-photometer at Aosta, (B) Aeronet sun-photometer at Rome TV, and (c) Aeronet sun-photometer at Hohenpeißenberg.

Rome.

This 24h-data is again relatively cloud free and shows an aerosol load in the boundary layer – which includes local urban pollution aerosols mixed with residual dust and local fires plumes. This site has co-located Aeronet sun-photometer providing AOD measurements and size distributions – shown in figure 3b. On 11 July 2017 two mass concentration profiles were measured using in situ instrumentation (a GRIMM particle counter) on board an aircraft. The times of these flights are indicated with vertical red lines in fig. 9.

Kleine Scheidegg.

This data, while relatively cloudy, shows aerosol plumes from a few hundred meters above the instrument up to around 2km (in range). Back trajectories indicate that the aerosol plumes are comprised of biomass burning aerosols. A particle counter located at the peak of Jungfrauoch around 1520m above the instrument and around 5km horizontal distance, provides aerosol mass concentrations for PM10.

Hohenpeißenberg.

The example data from this site was recorded during a desert dust event, again as confirmed by back trajectories. A co-located AERONET sun-photometer recorded the size distributions shown in fig. 3, the pronounced peak in the coarse mode is consistent with the aerosols being desert dust.

Also co-located with the CHM15k at this site is a PollyXT high powered lidar, operated and maintained by DWD. Data from this lidar is shown in fig. 4, the upper panel shows the log10 of the attenuated backscatter, and the lower panel shows the log10 of the volume depolarization ratio (VDR), both at 532nm. The PollyXT elastic data has been calibrated using a backward Klett method and the depolarisation is calibrated using the delta 45 technique (Freudenthaler et al. 2016). The data was processed using the EARLINET single calculus chain (D'Amico et al. 2015). The single calculus chain processing used to produce the data in figure 4 did not make use of any sun-photometer data. However, in section 4, sun-photometer data is used to calculate the EMC used in converting this data to mass estimates. The VDR shows that the aerosol layers up to around 4km are depolarising and are therefore likely to be irregularly shaped – again consistent with the aerosols containing desert dust.

Figure 4. Data from the Hohenpeißenberg EARLINET PollyXT lidar at 532nm for 21 June 2023. (A) attenuated backscatter and (B) volume depolarisation ratio. Breaks in the data are due to rain or low cloud.

These four data sets have been processed into extinction and mass concentration estimates using the three workflows described above. The next section shows the results.

4. Results.

Extinction products.

Figure 5 shows AOD values for the three sites having co-located sun-photometers. The plots thus show sun photometer measured AODs and relevant AOD calculated by integrating the ALCs extinction profiles (from the ground to 5 km range from the instrument). Note from the time axis that the data shown is only for the periods where the sun-photometers were able to record data (day light and cloud free). Any ALC profiles within these time periods that contained cloud below 5km were removed.

Overall, the ALC derived AODs show the same general trends, and are mostly within 25% of each other. The differences in magnitude are mostly due to the different choices in LR. When the same LR is used in each workflow the differences largely disappear. For example, the UK Met Office results were in nearly full agreement with the A-Profile results when a LR of 40sr was used in the UK Met Office workflow. The variable LR used by ALICENet is harder to assess. In the Aosta case the ALICENet LR varied with time and range between around 40sr and 50sr, and this would account for the AOD values lying between those of the Met Office (50sr) and A-profiles (40sr). As discussed in section 2, the ALICENet data for Hohenpeißenberg has been averaged to 15min resolution. This averaging is evident in the smoother AOD curve. Being optimized for ‘continental aerosol type’, the underestimation of Alicenet AOD inversion is an expected and known issue when desert dust dominates as in this case (e.g. Bellini et al., 2024). As also discussed above, an overlap temperature correction is not applied in the A-Profiles workflow, and this will also cause small variations between the ALC derived AODs due to the associated differences in the shape of the extinction profiles in the overlap region below around 1km.

In all, the AOD values from the three workflows are generally close to each other, and as expected, are mostly influenced by the choice of LR. The differences between the AOD values can mostly be explained by the choice of LR used in the backward Klett calculations, and differences caused by different averaging times and overlap correction are less important.

Figure 5. ALC derived (continuous lines) and sun-photometer measured (dots) AODs for selected dates. (A) Aosta, (B) Hohenpeißenberg and (C) Rome TV. Note that the times shown correspond only to the times the sun-photometers were measuring AOD. The ALC AODs were calculated by integrating the extinction profiles from the ground to 5km range from the instrument and are at 1064nm, the sun-photometer data are for 1020nm.

Compared to the sun-photometer AOD values, the influence of the choice of LR on the ALC derived AODs could again account for some of the differences. We note that the accuracy of the overall calibration of the L2 data will also influence the ALC AOD.

The ALC derived values for AOD at Aosta are relatively close to the sun-photometer values, with the ALICENet values being particularly close. The differences could be eliminated by using the sun-photometer AOD to constrain the choices of LR. We note that this functionality will be offered by the A-Profiles library in the future. It should be also noted that the very low aerosol loads recorded in the Aosta and Rome cases (AOD < 0.1) represent the most difficult condition for such evaluations. In fact, when analysed over a longer time frame (10 days of continuous measurements, as shown in Figure 6 for the Rome case), the ALC-derived AOD is found to mostly follow the day-by-day and diurnal variability of the sun-photometer AOD.

Figure 6. ALC derived AOD at 1064nm for each workflow at Rome, 4 July to 14 July 2017. The AOD at 1020nm recorded by the co-located AERONET sun-photometer is shown in black.

Overall, the results are compatible with the expected accuracies of the ALC-based AOD (these are estimated up to 40% for the Alicenet retrieval, Bellini et al., 2024)

Mass concentration products.

As described in section 2, to convert the ALC aerosol extinction profiles to aerosol mass concentration estimates a EMC is needed, and must be either assumed a-priori, or calculated in some way. Table 3 shows the EMCs used by the three workflows, and associated parameters.

Table 3. Summary of assumed values used in data the processing.

Location	LR [sr]	EMC [m²g⁻¹]	Assumed densities. [gcm⁻³]
Aosta	ALICEnet: variable 40-to-50 UK Met Office: 50 A-Profiles: 40	ALICEnet: variable 0.9 - 1.2 UK Met Office: 1.3 A-Profiles: 0.31	ALICEnet: 1.5 UK Met Office: 1.2 A-Profiles: 1.7
Rome TV	ALICEnet: variable 40-to-50 UK Met Office: 50 A-Profiles: 40	ALICEnet: variable 0.9 - 1.2 UK Met Office: 0.87 A-Profiles: 0.31	ALICEnet: 1.5 UK Met Office: 1.2 A-Profiles: 1.7
Hohenpeißenberg	ALICEnet: variable 40-to-50 UK Met Office: 50 A-Profiles: 40	ALICEnet: variable 0.9 - 1.2 ≈UK Met Office: 0.7 A-Profiles: 0.3	ALICEnet: 1.5 (also 2.5 see text) UK Met Office: 2.0 A-Profiles: 2.5
Kleine Scheidegg	ALICEnet: variable 40-to-50 UK Met Office: 50 A-Profiles: 40	ALICEnet: variable 0.9 - 1.2 UK Met Office: 1.3 A-Profiles: 0.68	ALICEnet: 1.5 UK Met Office: 1.2 A-Profiles: 1.15

Aosta.

Figure 7 shows the aerosol mass concentration results for Aosta for each workflow – the A-Profiles results are for “urban pollution”. The ALICEnet results are generally around 15% to 20% lower than the UK Met Office results, which is to be expected given the different choices of LRs and EMCs (see table 2). The A-Profiles mass concentrations are significantly larger than both the ALICEnet and UK Met Office results – more than double the ALICEnet results in some cases. Figure 8 shows the aerosol extinction, mass concentration and EMC profiles for Aosta averaged between 17:30 and 18:30. While the extinction profiles are in near agreement (except in the overlap region – again due to the temperature corrections not being applied in A-Profiles), the mass concentrations are more varied. Again, this is largely due to the much lower EMC of 0.31m²g⁻¹, compared to the values ~1 m²g⁻¹ and 1.3m²g⁻¹ used by ALICEnet and the UK Met Office, respectively.

Figure 7. Mass concentrations for each workflow for Aosta.

Without an in-situ measurement of the aerosol mass concentrations it is not possible to assess which EMC is most appropriate in this case – however this example illustrates how significant differences in the mass estimates can be introduced by the choice of EMCs, even when the extinction profiles were close.

Figure 8. Extinction, mass concentration and EMC profiles for Aosta on 26-05-2017 between 17:30 and 18:30

Rome TV.

Figure 9. Mass concentrations for each workflow for Rome TV data (vertical red lines indicate timing of the two flights equipped with in situ OPC data, see also Fig. 10).

Figure 9 shows the aerosol mass concentration results for Rome TV for each workflow – the A-Profiles results are again for “urban pollution” although a very mixed condition characterized that period (both dust and biomass burning thin layer were present). In general, the variation between the mass concentration estimates from each workflow are similar to those in the Aosta example. The ALICENet results are generally around 30% to 20% lower than the UK Met Office results, and the A-Profiles mass concentrations are again significantly larger than both the ALICENet and UK Met Office results, often more than double the ALICENet results.

Figure 10. Mass concentrations for each workflow for Rome. (A) Averaged between 08:25 and 08:36, and (B) averaged between 12:17 and 12:29. In each plot the GRIMM OPC mass concentration is shown in black. This is a 90m running average over the GRIMM data points shown as blue dots.

Figure 10 shows mass concentration profiles for Rome from the three workflows, averaged between 08:25 and 08:36, and between 12:17 and 12:29 on 11 July 2017. Also shown in the plots are data points from the GRIMM OPC on board an aircraft that performed profiles above the Rome TV site between those times, these indicating a large variability in the in-situ measurements themselves. The black curve is a 90m (6 altitude bins) running average over the GRIMM data points. Note that the y-axis starts at 250m – the lowest level at which the GRIMM collected data. At this stage we have made no adjustment for particle hydration, or for particle losses / modification in the aircraft intake, and these could be further explored.

While the ALC profiles and the OPC profiles are slightly different in shape, the ALICENet results are close to the GRIMM OPC, in some cases in very good agreement, particularly during the first flight. Overall, these are mostly within the 50% uncertainty expected to be associated to the ALICENet-estimated aerosol mass (Dionisi et al., 2018; Bellini et al., 2024). The UK Met Office estimates are larger in magnitude than both the ALICENet and the OPC data. The A-Profiles results are again more than twice the ALICENet results, and in this case also of the OPC data. We note that mass concentrations from OPCs have some uncertainty – the refractive index for latex spheres is used in the OPC calibration, meaning that more absorbing / scattering particles can be undersized, leading to a too small measurement of particle volume. The OPC data has been processed assuming a particle density of 1.5 g cm^{-3} – which is a further source of uncertainty. However, these considerations notwithstanding, it appears from these data that the EMC of $0.31 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ used by A-Profiles for urban pollution may not have been appropriate in this case, and that used by ALICENet (variable around $1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), and the UK Met Office ($0.87 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) were more appropriate.

Kleine Scheidegg.

The results from each workflow for Kleine Scheidegg are shown in figure 11. The A-Profiles results are for “biomass burning”. As there is no sun-photometer data available at this site, the EMC used in the UK Met Office workflow is a default value for biomass burning aerosol. This was calculated from historic AERONET data (from 2011 to present) recorded at sites across Europe when impacted by biomass burning aerosol plumes. The ALICENet data were obtained with the standard procedure (i.e. not tuned for a BB aerosol type) and have been averaged to 15min and cloud screened, as against 5min for the UK Met Office and A-Profiles results.

Figure 11. Mass concentrations for each workflow for Kleine Scheidegg case study. .

Again, in general the mass concentration estimates from ALICENet and the UK Met Office are often within 15% of each other. The A-Profiles results are closer to those from the other two workflows this time, often within 20% of the UK Met office, and 30% of the ALICENet results.

Figure 12 shows the aerosol extinction, mass concentration and EMC profiles for Kleine Scheidegg averaged between 09:20 and 09:30. As discussed above, the different choices of LR in each workflow have led to differences in the extinction profiles, with the A-Profiles extinction being generally smaller than the others. However, in the mass concentrations plot, this situation is reversed, with the A-Profiles mass estimate being the larger of the three. This is due once again to the A-Profiles EMC ($0.68\text{m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$) being smaller than those used by ALICENet (variable around $1\text{m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$) and the UK Met Office ($1.1\text{m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$).

Figure 12. Extinction, mass concentration and EMC profiles for Kleine Scheidegg between 09:20 and 09:40.

The hourly mean mass estimates at 1km and at 2km range for each workflow are shown in shown in fig 13. Also shown are the hourly mean measurements from the particle counter at Jungfrauoch (around 4 km horizontal distance apart). We note that the in situ particle counter is at around 1.3km above the CHM15k, but we chose 1km and 2km range for investigating the ALC data as being the range at which aerosol layers are evident at around the same time as the peak concentrations measured by the particle counter at Jungfrauoch. While shifted in time, likely due to the distance between the measurements, the ALC mass estimates are on the same order of magnitude as the peak values recorded by the particle counter. Given the variability introduced by the advection of the biomass burning plume as it was transported from above the CHM15k site to Jungfrauoch the ALC estimates are in fair agreement. It is not possible to state which of the EMC was most suitable in this case, as all have resulted in mass estimates that are close to the particle counter measurements.

Figure 13. Time series of hourly mean mass concentrations from ALC at 1km and 2km (color), and from the Jungfrauoch particle counter (black). Solid lines indicate the particle mass at 1km, and dashed lined the same at 2km. Gaps in the data indicate where the retrievals are not performed due to clouds detected.

Hohenpeißenberg.

Fig 14 shows the mass results from each workflow for Hohenpeißenberg. The A-Profiles results are for “dust”. The ALICENet results were again obtained with the standard procedure (i.e. for a continental aerosol type, and not tuned for a desert dust aerosol type), are averaged to 15 min resolution and cloud screened. Similarly to the other sites, the ALICENet mass estimates give the lowest values followed by the UK Met Office estimates, and then A-Profiles – once again reflecting the different EMCs used: $1.1 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$, $0.7 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ and $0.3 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ respectively.

Figure 14. Mass concentrations for each workflow for Hohenpeißenberg case studies. Alicenet data in the top panel are cloud screened.

Figure 15 shows the ALC mass estimates averaged between 04:00 and 06:00, and a mass estimate from the PollyXT lidar at Hohenpeißenberg for the same time window (calculated using a backwards Klett method, $\text{LR}=50\text{sr}$, and a EMC of $0.7 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ which was obtained from the Aeronet data and an assumed density of 2.5 gcm^{-3} following the Polyphon process (Ansmann et al. 2019)). Figure 15 also shows the PollyXT depolarisation ratios (volume and particle), and the respective EMCs used to obtain each mass estimate profile.

The ALC derived mass estimates shown in figure 15 are significantly lower than the PollyXT estimate – with the default settings ALICenet values often only around 30% of the PollyXT values. However, the PollyXT mass estimates are influenced by the same issues as the ALC derived estimates, and as such cannot be considered as a “Truth” value and is shown here as a comparison only. The difference between the ALC estimates (at 1064nm) and those from the PollyXT data (532nm) could be due to using EMCs for pure dust where depolarization values indicate the dust aerosol to be in fact mixed (likely with a smaller, more efficiently scattering aerosol such as urban pollution or marine aerosol). Such a situation would result in the mass estimates being too large, and may affect shorter wavelengths more, as the extinction angstrom exponent would likely be large for smaller particles. The particle depolarisation ratios (PDR) suggest that the aerosol present is a dusty mixture, with the values largely being around 20%. Literature values for PDR for pure dust are around 30-40% for pure dust at 532nm (e.g. Illingworth et al. 2015, Gross et al. 2019).

As mentioned, the polynomial fit used in the current ALICenet algorithm inversion is assuming a continental aerosol, and this will underestimate particle volume when a different type of aerosol is present. This is particularly true for the presence of coarse and nonspherical particles as is the case of desert dust (e.g. Barnaba and Gobbi 2001). The default density of 1.5gcm^{-3} used in the ALICenet workflow will also result in underestimated mass concentrations when denser particles are present. To make the workflow results more comparable for this example, the ALICenet workflow result (this providing aerosol volume not mass) were also converted into mass using a density more appropriate for desert dust (2.5 gcm^{-3}), and this is shown in figure 15 as a dashed orange line. The ALICenet mass estimates are then very similar to the UK Met Office results. In all, given the uncertainty of around 50% on the mass estimates from the various workflows (Dionisi et al., 2018, Osborne et al. 2019), the mass estimates from the three workflows are consistent with each other and with the Polly XT estimates.

5. Conclusion.

We have presented a comparison between the extinction and mass concentration estimates derived from CHM15k data using three different workflows. All three use a forward Klett method, relying on the EPROFILE calibration of the L2 data files. Other than differences introduced by the different choices of LR (and some small differences due to averaging and overlap correction strategy) the extinction products are very similar – this was expected to be the case given the similar methods employed by each workflow. Compared to co-located sun-photometer AOD measurements, the AOD values derived from the ALC extinction profiles show some differences, possibly caused by the assumed values of LR. The sun-photometer values could be matched by using a suitable and variable LR. Where possible, it may be an advantage to use sun-photometer measurements to constrain the LR to ensure that the ALC AOD values match the sun-photometer values. This will hopefully be available in the A-Profiles library in the future.

Figure 15 Mass concentrations, depolarization ratios and EMCs for Hohenpeißenberg. Averaged between 04:00 and 06:00. The orange dashed lines shows the result of using a density of 2.5 g cm^{-3} which is more appropriate for desert dust in the ALICEnet workflow.

The magnitude of mass estimates from each workflow showed some larger differences according to the choice of EMC. Again, this was expected to be the case, and it is well known that the EMC is a vital consideration when converting extinction to mass concentration estimates. In the case of urban pollution, the A-Profiles mass estimates were much larger than those from the other two workflows, and often double those from ALICEnet. For the data from Rome TV, the ALICEnet results were closest to the “truth” value from the aircraft OPC – although we note that OPCs have their own uncertainties. The OPC uncertainties are difficult to quantify, and they result from aerosol modification at the aircraft inlets, from non-idealised responses of the OPC, and from calibration using materials with refractive indices different from the particles being sampled – however, they are likely to be on the order of 25% (Johnson et al. 2012, Rosenberg et al. 2012, Spanu et al. 2020). In the case of biomass burning aerosols, the results from the three workflows were much closer, and all were within a reasonable range of the particle counter at Jungfraujoch. For the dust case, the ALC mass estimates were all below

that obtained from the PollyXT data – possibly due to the use of EMCs for pure dust, when in fact the aerosol was a dusty mixture.

In summary the results indicate that each workflow results in reasonable extinction and mass estimates. However, as was expected, the assumed EMCs are a vital consideration when calculating mass estimates from calibrated ALC data. The literature provides EMCs for various aerosols and aerosol mixtures at 355nm and 532nm, but there seems to be a limited amount of data for 1064nm (some preliminary review is provided in Dionisi et al., 2018, Table 5). We recommend that the community puts some focus on obtaining a climatology of EMC factors for a range of aerosols and aerosol mixtures at 1064nm – the CHM15k transmission wavelength, and also at 910nm – the transmission wavelength of the recently available polarization-sensitive ALC (PLC) by Vaisala (CL61 model).

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